

Students' Response of Using Cornell Note Taking System (CNTS) in Listening Class

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Abstract: The main concern of the present study is to investigate the students' response in CNTS in Literal Listening. This study employs descriptive qualitative method. It involves 18 students who enrolled in Literal Listening Class. Data was gathered through questionnaire and interview. The results of the study showed that note taking was still presumably considered as difficult skill because most lecturers were still not familiar to it. Consequently the students often struggle to decide what to note as the lecturers do not tell what to include in note. However, Cornell Note Taking System was generally proven helpful study tool in listening activity particularly it is because CNTS was a systematic guided note that perceived to be very helpful for students to be a good note taker. Suggestions are proposed for teacher particularly to prepare students with techniques of what to note and introduce it earlier so that it would become the students' habit. The results of this study may also be addressed for those who are interested in this field particularly English lecturers or lecturers who have problems in teaching listening.

Keywords: *Cornell Note Taking System, Students' Response, Literal Listening*

INTRODUCTION

Listening skill is a complex process that allows us to understand oral language in language teaching (Rost: 2001). It is also the ability to understand what others people are saying. It can be concluded that that understanding a speaker accent or pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary, and also comprehending the meaning of the speaker saying is called as listening (Saricoban, 1999). In addition to, Rost as cited in Harrouz (2016) explained that listening is the essential aspects that we use in everyday life. Furthermore Malkawi (2010) found that students listen for about 45 percent of the

time they spend in communication. He also found that 30 percent of communication time was spent by speaking, 16 percent for reading, and only 9 percent for writing. In other words, students spend most of their time more in listening. It can be therefore concluded that listening becomes a very significant and challenging skill in acquiring foreign language particularly for EFL learners.

However, though it is significant and challenging. In fact, students still felt difficult to catch the ideas while listening because of some bad habits. G. Nichols as cited in Meysarah (2012) stated that there are ten bad habits while listening as follows:

1. Uninteresting subject

Students oftenly found unknown and difficult words while listening to an audio passage. Unluckily they intend to focus on those word and eventually decide that it is a subject of the passage.

2. Judging delivery, not content

Students sometimes easily draw a conclusion directly eventhough they have not finished listening the whole passage yet. Due to that, they often judge wrong content.

3. Involving excessive emotional

A sufficient warm up should be given prior to to listening activity to ignite their concentration. An excessive emotional involvement would prevent them focus in listening.

4. Listening for details, not central ideas

Students oftenly spend most of their time figuring out unknown words while listening. Consequently, they missed the central idea. In addition to, lack of vocabulary is presumably the additional problem.

5. Irrelevant topics

Students' prior knowledge determines their ability to draw conclusion are trapped in their own conclusion about the topic.

6. Paying poor attention to the speaker

Transition signals uttered by the speaker are sometimes misinterpreted by the students due to lack of attention. Those signals are getting unclear as in pauses, gestures, a clear change of pitch, or different intonation patterns.

7. Easily distracted

As EFL learners, students have less interaction with native speakers. Consequently their attention will be easily distracted while listening to native speakers. Adank et al (2009) added that to comprehend an unfamiliar native accent was slightly equal to comprehending a familiar accent in quiet condition. It is a result of their ability of listening in slow rate. Therefore, they require more time to think or listen twice as the speaker says using speed of native speech.

8. Avoiding difficult material

Lecturers often tend to avoid difficult material to make the students easier to listen and comprehend the material. It would be very helpful at the very beginning. However, they would face lots of difficulties in exercise practice or in listening test.

9. Refusing to accept new ideas.

New ideas or information are mostly refused by the students due to their lack of background knowledge. As a result, they would listen to unnecessary ideas or information.

10. Nonflexible note taking system.

Most of students still do not have note taking experience while listening. They do not know what information should be noted or not. Consequently, lots of the students tend to write everything they hear. The students therefore need to be exposed to a flexible and note taking system in order to make their listening activities effective and efficient.

The fore mentioned habits are in line with the result of interview and observation conducted prior to the research particularly in the last point that is note taking system. The result of the interview reveals that all of the students do not have any sufficient note taking experience while listening. Even they seldom to take some note while listening. Based on the interview, most of the students stated that they do not know what to write while listening. They thought that everything they listen would be

necessary information. Eventually, they would face lots of difficulties to select the necessary or unnecessary information while listening. As a result, most of them usually find difficulties in choosing or answering questions in listening test. Eventually they seldom achieve good mark in listening.

An effective and flexible note taking system is required to help students avoid the fore mentioned bad habits in listening. Marzano et al (2001) stated that note-taking system is the way to assist students to improve their academic achievement. The ultimate goal is to prevent students forgetting. Forgetting happens to most students rapidly after listening or reading although the material is sometimes very interesting. In addition to, several researches also reveal that 50% of what we hear forgotten within an hour and more than 70% within two days. Furthermore, a student is required to be mentally active taking note during listening or reading effectively. The students should be attentive, active, and decisive while listening or reading particularly about what to record, and write.

Cornell Note Taking System or henceforth abbreviated as CNTS is proposed to be an effective and flexible note taking system. CNTS was originally created by Dr. Walter Pauk, the lecturer of Cornell University. CNTS is a two column system; the left column is one third of the page, and the right column is two thirds of the page (Faber et al., 2000). The right column is used to catch the key ideas and facts. The left column is filled with questions relating to the main points. Having finished the note-taking session, students are required to review their notes and write questions in the cue column to highlight main points, meanings, and relationships. The process of writing the questions in the cue column helps clarify meanings, reveal relationships, establish continuity, and strengthen memory. This column is also used in the review process when notes are studied. At the bottom of the page, a two inch-space is left for summarizing the main point(s) of the page, which again clarifies meanings and also makes review easier (Pauk, 2001). When the note column, cue column and summary area are used for note-taking and for review, students have an organized system that can improve comprehension and achievement. CNTS also enables students to organize and review their note to increase

their comprehension and critical thinking whether in listening or in reading. Furthermore, the biggest benefit of using CNTS is the students can note any ideas related to the topic they listen or read. They are also required to make a summary using their own words in the end of the note based on the questions provided.

Based on the background fore-mentioned above, the researcher wants to conduct a research about students' response of using Cornell note-taking system in listening class. It is different from previous studies because here the researcher investigates Cornell note-taking system in listening skill particularly in literal listening viewed from students' responses.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive qualitative was selected to be the research design. It has a purpose to investigate a case in depth. In this case, the researcher investigated the students' responses. Ary et. al., (2010) stated that qualitative research is a research that investigates the quality of relationships, activities, situations, and materials. The focus of the study was in students' responses on the use of using CNTS in listening class, especially in students' literal listening skills. The main instruments of this research was questionnaire. This study was held in English Department STKIP Al Hikmah Surabaya, especially in literal listening class. The subject of this study was the 18 students who attended Literal Listening Class.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings to the first questionnaire item which was asking if note taking to be an easy skill. It is revealed that 22,2 % of the students replied that note taking was a very easy skill. 55,6% of them stated that note taking was sometimes an easy skill. 16,7% of them stated that note taking was rarely an easy skill. While the rest of them (5.5%) stated that note taking was a very difficult skill. The result in details was shown in the following chart.

It can be concluded that note taking is still presumably a difficult skill for EFL learners. It is line with Piolat et al (2004) who stated that note-taking is a complex activity that combines comprehension with production of notes, and this complicated process is dependent upon working memory. Furthermore, Cohn et al (1995) stated that listen to a lecture, the important information should be held in working memory long enough to access it as they write it down. In addition to, note-taking is dependent on working memory to “acquire, mentally represent, select and understand the incoming information while making connections with previous knowledge (Makany, Kemp, & Dror, 2009, p. 620)

The response to the second questionnaire item was asking how often students take note in listening class. The responses were 50% of the students always take note in listening class. 33.3% of them sometimes take note in listening class. 16.7% of them rarely take note in listening class. The result in details was shown in the following chart.

It revealed that note taking was still not a students' habit. It was relevant to G. Nichols as cited in Meysarah (2012) who stated that most of students still do not have note taking experience while listening. They do not know what information should be noted or not. Consequently, lots of the students tend to write everything they hear. The students therefore need to be exposed to a flexible and note taking system in order to make their listening activities effective and efficient.

The third questionnaire item was asking if the lecturer provide students with guided note. The responses were 16.7% of the students replied that the lecturer always provide them with guided note. 61.1% of the students stated that the lecturer provide their students with guided note. 11.1% of the students stated that the lecturer rarely provide them with guided note. While 11.1% students stated that the lecturer never provided them with guided note. The result in details was shown in the following chart.

It showed that guided note while listening was proven necessary. It definitely supports Gray & Madson (2007) who stated that when students are shown a structure for note-taking, it often improves the quality of their notes. In addition to, Faber et al. (2000) showed that students who were taught the Cornell method had significantly better scores than the students who were not taught this method.

The fourth questionnaire item was asking if it is available whether guided notes or un-guided note is preferable. The responses were 38.9% of the students replied that guided note is preferable, 30.9% of the students chose un-guided note and 22.2%

students did not select whether guided or un-guided note. The result in details was shown in the following chart.

The finding above revealed that guided note is more preferable than un-guided note. It was in line with Hayati & Jalilifar (2009) who stated in their finding that students instructed in taking notes revealed significantly better results than students who took notes in their own manner or students who did not take any notes. Their results revealed a positive impact of note taking instruction on listening comprehension.

The fifth questionnaire item was asking if students review the note before answering question. The responses were 61.1% of the students always review their note before answering the question. 22.2% of them sometimes review their note before answering the question while 16.7% of them rarely review their note before answering the question. The result in details was shown in the following chart.

It revealed that most students reviewed their note before answering question. It is in line with Boran and Yi (2012) who believed that note-taking consists of four skills,

namely “listening, cognitive processing, recording passage content in written form and reviewing noted information.

The sixth questionnaire item was asking if Cornell Note Taking System (CNTS) was a helpful study tool in listening class. The responses were 72.2 % of the students stated that CNTS to be helpful study tool in listening class. While 27.8% of them replied that CNTS was sometimes to be a helpful study tool in listening class. The result in details was shown in the following chart.

The finding above revealed that CNTS was proven to be a helpful study tool in listening class. It supports Faber et al.(2000) showed that students who were taught the Cornell method had significantly better scores than the students who were not taught this method.

The seventh questionnaire item was asking if it is difficult using Cornell Note Taking System (CNTS) in listening class. The responses were 33.3 % of the students stated that it is always difficult using CNTS to take note in listening class. 44.4% of them replied that it is sometimes difficult using CNTS in listening class. While 22.2% of them stated that is rarely difficult using CNTS to take note in listening class. The result in details was shown in the following chart.

It revealed that using CNTS was still presumably difficult for some students. It is relevant to G. Nichols as cited in Meysarah (2012) who stated that most of students still do not have note taking experience while listening. They do not know what information should be noted or not. Consequently, lots of the students tend to write everything they hear. The students therefore need to be exposed to a flexible and note taking system in order to make their listening activities effective and efficient.

The eighth questionnaire item was asking if students struggle deciding what to include in note using Cornell Note Taking System (CNTS) in listening class. The responses were 29.4 % of the students stated that they always struggle deciding what to include in note using CNTS. 58.8% of them replied that they are sometimes struggle deciding what to include in note using CNTS. While 11.8% of them stated that they rarely struggle deciding what to include in note using CNTS. The result in details was shown in the following chart.

The finding above showed that most students found difficulties deciding what to include in their note using CNTS. It confirmed the finding of Boyle (2007) and Faber et al.(2000) who stated that students are not taught how to take notes, or are taught these skills at a relatively late point in the course of their education. In addition to, Power as cited in Flowerdew (1994) who stated that taking note during a lecture required specific skills.

The ninth questionnaire item was asking if lecturers tell students what to include in note while using Cornell Note Taking System (CNTS) in listening class. The responses were 23.5 % of the students stated that the lecturer always told them what to include in note using CNTS. 58.8% of them replied that the lecturer sometimes told them what to include in note using CNTS. 11.8% of them stated that the lecturer rarely told them what to include in note using CNTS. While 5.9% of them stated that the lecturer never told them what to include in note using CNTS. The result in details was shown in the following chart.

The finding above indicated us that most lecturers are still unfamiliar to CNTS. Therefore the lecturers require to follow steps in note taking as suggested by Marzano (2001) that are preparing, questioning, and summarizing. In preparing stage, the lecturer should explain what to include while using CNTS.

The tenth questionnaire item was asking if the students copy down their note using Cornell Note Taking System (CNTS). The responses were 22.2 % of the students stated that they always copy down their note in CNTS. 44.4% of them replied that they

sometimes copy down their note in CNTS. 16.7% of them stated that they rarely copy down their note in CNTS. While 16.7% of them stated that they never copy down in note using CNTS. The result in details was shown in the following chart.

The above finding indicated that most of the students copy down their note in CNTS. It showed that they still had difficulties to identify and understand the most important aspects of what they are learning (Marzano, Pickering, & Pollock, 2001, p. 48).

The eleventh questionnaire item was asking if using Cornell Note Taking System (CNTS) help the students be a good note taker. The responses were 11.1 % of the students stated that CNTS helps them to be a good note taker. 50% of the students replied that CNTS sometimes helps them to be good note taker. 27.8% of them stated that CNTS rarely helps them to be good a note taker. While 11.1% of them stated that CNTS helps them to be a good note taker. The result in details was shown in the following chart.

The finding above confirmed that CNTS was effectively proven to help students to be a good note taker. It is in line with Hayati (2009) who stated that CNTS is acceptable for students who are new in listening class, because the format is easy to take the key words and concepts. Consequently, the students do not waste their time to think others material. In addition to, Cornell Note Taking System is claimed by Anjarsit et al., (2017) that it is an effective way to take a note, because it is organized system or ideas that help the students in taking a note

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the findings and discussion previously elaborated, it can be concluded that students' response towards CNTS can be classified as follows : note taking is still presumably as a difficult skill. Since it is complex process that combines comprehension with production of notes, and this complicated process is dependent upon working memory. As a result note taking was still not a students' habit particularly in listening. Therefore, guided note while listening was proven necessary. In addition to, guided notes or un-guided note is preferable. Students using guided notes achieved significantly better results than students who use unguided note. It is because most students reviewed their note before answering question.

As a guided note, CNTS was perceived to be a helpful study tool in listening class. However, CNTS was still presumably difficult for some students. As a result, students still struggle deciding what to include in note using Cornell Note Taking System (CNTS) in listening class. Most students found difficulties deciding what to include in their note using CNTS. Consequently, most students found difficulties deciding what to include in their note using CNTS. Therefore, students tend to copy down all their note. Unfortunately, most lecturers do not tell students what to include in note while using Cornell Note Taking System (CNTS) in listening class. Lastly, CNTS however was still generally perceived to help students to be a good note taker.

However, students' responses previously elaborated lead to several suggestions. Firstly, lecturers are required to train students of how to use CNTS including explaining

the use of clues, notes and summary elaboratively. Then, lecturers need to show a model of how to take note using CNTS so that students would eventually find out what to include in note and how to review the note before summarizing it. Therefore, students would not struggle to decide what to include in their note. In short, note taking would be very effective.

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